

ATLAS New Small Wheel performance studies with first data of LHC Run3

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17-21 July 2023

Abstract

After successfully completing Phase I upgrades during LHC Long Shutdown 2, the ATLAS detector is back in operation with several upgrades implemented. The most important and challenging upgrade is in the muon spectrometer, where the two inner forward muon stations have been replaced with the New Small Wheels (NSW) system featuring two entirely new detector technologies: small strip Thin Gap Chambers (sTGC) and the Micromegas (MMG). Following the massive build, test and installation work in ATLAS, the two endcap NSW were used in the first collision data period in 2022 participating in the Muon Spectrometer tracking system, at the same time completing the phase of commissioning of this completely new system. A huge effort has gone into the operation of the new data acquisition system, as well as the implementation of a new processing chain within the muon software framework. The new detectors are fully integrated into the software. Tracking is performed with full consideration of the absolute alignment of each individual detector module by the ATLAS Muon Spectrometer optical alignment system. All the deviations from the nominal geometry of all the constituent elements of each sTGC and MM module are accounted for through the modeling of the real chamber geometry reconstructed from the information of the construction databases. After an overview of the software implementation and the strategies adopted for the simulations and reconstruction, the studies on the performance of the NSW system from the first months of 2022 Run3 data taking will be reported.

1 Introduction

The ATLAS experiment [3, 4] at the LHC is a multipurpose particle detector with a forward–backward symmetric cylindrical geometry and a near 4π coverage in solid angle. It consists of an inner tracking detector surrounded by a thin superconducting solenoid providing a 2T axial magnetic field, electromagnetic and hadron calorimeters, and a muon spectrometer (MS). The ATLAS experiment has completed the Phase-I upgrade to the MS during the LHC Long Shutdown 2 that ended in 2022. The two inner forward muon stations have been replaced with the New Small Wheels (NSW) system. The NSW system is designed to provide fast trigger and precision tracking in the forward region of ATLAS, towards the MS operation at the future High Luminosity LHC (HL-LHC). To satisfy the requirement of working with an instantaneous luminosity of over 5 times the nominal design value, the NSW must record the tracking segment with 15% resolution at 1-TeV transverse momentum (p_T) scale, and with 97% efficiency for tracks with p_T above 10 GeV. Besides, the NSW is required to have an angular resolution of 1 mrad for its track reconstruction, to enhance the ATLAS Level-1 trigger in the forward region by injecting additional segment measurement between the inner detector and the outer stations of MS. Two entirely new gaseous detector technologies: small strip Thin Gap Chambers (sTGC) [1] and the Micromegas (MMG) [2], are employed in the NSW to achieve the design objective.

2 NSW Detector Description

The MMG detectors are large-area micro-pattern gaseous detectors (MPGDs), each layer consists of a 5-mm drift gap, a 120- μm amplification gap, and a grounded metallic mesh which separates the two gaps. The mesh structure is supported by the readout plane that contains capacitively coupled resistive strips and readout strips with a pitch of 450 μm . The working gas is the mixture of Ar: CO₂:iC₄H₁₀ (93:5:2). It has been demonstrated to improve the high-voltage stability comparing with the standard Ar:CO₂ (93:7) mixture.

The unit of the sTGC detector is a multi-wire ionization chamber, consisting of two cathodes planes and anode wires between the planes. One of the two cathodes planes has 3.2-mm pitch readout strips, and the other has relatively lower readout granularity to provide fast triggering. The two readout system are named respectively as “Strip” and “Pad”. The wires have finer pitch to provide track reconstruction in the transverse direction. The sTGC system is circulated with the mixture of CO₂:n-pentane (55:45).

The NSW detectors are installed at the two sides of the ATLAS end-cap. Each wheel is constructed as a disk-like structure including 16 sectors, and each sector is comprised of two sTGC quadruplets, and two MMG quadruplets between the sTGC quadruplets. In any sector, there are 8 layers of sTGCs and 8 layers of MMGs. Limited by the working-area size of MMG and sTGC, three sets of quadruplets are arranged from the innermost to outermost to form one sector. In total the two wheels provide a detecting area greater than 2400 m², contributed by roughly 2.1 M MMG readout channels and 0.3 M sTGC channels.

The data acquisition (DAQ) system contains two types of radiation-tolerant front-end ASICs: VMM [6] and ROC [5], and many Level-1 data driver cards [7] connecting ASICs with 4.8 Gbps duplex optical links. The VMMs are connected to the readout electrodes to provide signal amplification, shaping and digitization. Data from VMMS are aggregated by the ROC ASICs, and transferred to the Front-End Link eXchange (FELIX) platform [9] designed for the LHC Run-3 and beyond to distribute the timing, trigger and control signals to the front-end electronics, and to transmit the level-1 data packets to the network server for reconstruction and triggering.

The construction of the NSW was initialized in Oct. 2017, and finalized in 2021. Both wheels were successfully installed in the ATLAS detector at the end of 2021, and the commission

continued till the April of 2023.

3 NSW performance in Run-3 data-taking

The NSW has been fully connected with detector services including high voltage (HV), low voltage (LV), gas, cooling and monitoring [10]. Approximately 99% of MMG HV channels and 98% of sTGC HV channels are working robustly during Run-3 data-taking.

The DAQ system is commissioned by adjusting the phase alignments between VMM and ROC, between ROC and level-1 data driver, and between the front-end electronics and FELIX. Moreover, the baseline, threshold, peak and charge output of VMM are dejectedly calibrated. Furthermore, the arrival time latency is adjusted to ensure all data hits are captured to improve the efficiency.

The NSW participated in the ATLAS level-1 forward muon trigger since May 2023 after commission using collision data [8]. In a candidate event, the coincidence of sTGC Pad readout defines a smaller region of interest and selects fast charge informace from a band of strips for accurate hit position reconstruction. For MMG, the earliest threshold-crossing strips are utilized to reconstruct a slope pointing to interaction point. The joining of NSW trigger has successfully reduced the muon level-1 trigger rate by approximately 25%.

The readout chain is integrated into the ATLAS muon reconstruction system such that the track segments reconstructed from MMG and sTGC are combined with the segments from other muon subsystems and the inner tracker. For both sTGC and MMG, the averaging segment cluster size is four to five, determined by the inherent inefficiency, as well as in-situ detector or DAQ in-capabilities. A significant fraction of problematic HV channels and electronics were fixed during the year-end technical stop, which globally improved the efficiency. Fig. 1 shows the four over eight (layers) efficiencies from data taken in May 2023. The global efficiency after combining sTGC and MMG efficiencies is above 95%. The source of inefficiency includes the crack between quadruplets, the DAQ instability and HV disabilities. The influenced region differs among data-taking runs.

Figure 1: Efficiencies for having at least four out of eight layers of (left) sTGC strips, (middle) MMG, and (right) combined associated to muon tracks with p_T above 15 GeV passing through the NSW for the run 452163 recorded on May 14th 2023. The two wheels are shown respectively at the top and bottom.

The position resolution are shown respectively for MMG and sTGC in Fig. 2 Spoiled by effects from the residual misalignment and the as-built geometry, the performance of MMG and STGC is degraded. An optical based alignment system has been installed for tracking the movement and deformation of the NSW. Exclusive optimization is continued benefiting from the alignment system and toroid-ff runs.

Figure 2: (a): Micromegas position resolution extracted by comparing the cluster position on two neighboring layers corrected by the track angle. (b): sTGC resolution for different values of the charge calibration of the readout electronics.

4 Conclusion

The New Small Wheel is the largest ATLAS phase-I upgrade project. Two wheels with large-area novel gaseous muon detectors have been successfully constructed and deployed in the ATLAS after years of efforts. Both sTGC and MMG detectors have been fully commissioned and the NSW joined the ATLAS Run-3 data taking since the very first day with outstanding performance. The overall efficiency is above 95%, and the NSW trigger has significantly reduced the level-1 muon trigger rate in the forward region. Due to the absence of particular calibrations, the designed value of position resolution hasn't been achieved.

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